

ISic1456

I.Sicily inscription 1456

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Territory of

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8783

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Φιλῖνος

2. Δίωνος

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284904

EDR 112486

EDCS 41300084

PHI 175698

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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